

MOBILE COMMUNICATION SECURITY DEFENSE METHOD BASED ON HONEYPOT TECHNOLOGY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6571331>

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First, honeypot technology is used to collect unknown threat information on mobile terminals, and then unknown threat intrusion detection rules are set to draw the threat path. Finally, honeypot technology is combined to establish an intelligent defense model for unknown threats on mobile terminals. In the era of industrial Internet, the development trend of digitization, networking, and intelligence has made more and more industrial control equipment that are originally in a closed environment exposed to the public Internet, facing the threat of attacks from the Internet. Moreover, honeypot is a new type of active defense technology, which attracts hackers to launch attacks by disguising as devices and systems that seem to be valuable. After capturing and analyzing the attack behavior, it understands the attack tools and methods, and guesses the attacker's intention and motivation. Based on the utilization of an unsupervised clustering algorithm, an information classification method is proposed in the paper. First, honeypots attack behaviors are captured with high and low interaction. Then, through redirection technology, normal access requests are forwarded to the real server for processing, and abnormal accesses are forwarded to the honeypot virtual machine to deal with. Finally, by selecting traditional tools for comparative testing, the experiment proves that the algorithm proposed in the paper can well defend and monitor as well as discover the behavior and information of the above attack events.

Attacks on the internet keep on increasing and it causes harm to our security system. In order to minimize this threat, it is necessary to have a security system that has the ability to detect zero-day attacks and block them. "Honeypot is the proactive defense technology, in which resources placed in a network with the aim to observe and capture new attacks". This paper proposes a honeypot-based model for intrusion detection system (IDS) to obtain the best useful data about the attacker. The

ability and the limitations of Honeypots were tested and aspects of it that need to be improved were identified. In the future, we aim to use this trend for early prevention so that pre-emptive action is taken before any unexpected harm to our security system.

Honeypot technology is a highly deceptive security protection technology, which can run in a variety of networks and terminal systems with characteristic vulnerabilities deliberately. Meanwhile, honeypot technology can induce intruders to launch attacks. Therefore, the source of the attack can be captured to realize security defenses, protecting important system terminals from infringement. Moreover, by inducing the intruder to attack the honeypot terminal, it can not only delay the time to attack the real target, but also timely monitor, collect and analyze the attack behavior to provide support for dealing with unknown threats. So, in order to solve the problems of traditional methods and apply honeypot technology to the process of unknown threat defense of mobile terminal, an intelligent defense method is proposed in the paper for mobile terminal unknown threats based on honeypot technology. The results of comparative experiments prove that the method proposed in the paper has less underreporting of unknown threats, and can fully detect the source information, which can meet the needs of mobile terminals for effective defense against unknown threats.

A honeypot is a network device that tricks hackers into thinking they've broken into an organization's real network when actually they are in a fake network set up as a trap. Once lured into a honeypot, an attacker's activities can be monitored and analyzed. Honeypots are designed to attract hackers, and the more convincing they are, the more successful they will be.

Attackers breaking into a honeypot believe they have hacked a legitimate part of the target network where they might find valuable data, critical applications or vulnerable parts of the network infrastructure. In reality, they are in an isolated computer system set up to keep them away from the production network and enable the target organization to track their movements and activities.

Researchers, businesses and consumers all use honeypots. Users monitor trapped attackers to gather information about their behavior and the types of attacks they employ. Network administrators can then use this information to strengthen their organization's cybersecurity strategy and infrastructure against future attacks

Honeypots are decoy systems or servers deployed alongside production systems within your network. When deployed as enticing targets for attackers, honeypots can add security monitoring opportunities for blue teams and misdirect the adversary from their true target. Honeypots come in a variety of complexities depending on the needs of your organization and can be a significant line of defense when it comes to flagging attacks early. This page will get into more detail on what honeypots are, how they are used, and the benefits of implementing them.

Honeypot forensics is used to study and understand a hacker strategy and his tools but not to prosecute him. This science is very time consuming and according to honeynet

project members, one hour of hacker activity can lead to more than 40h of forensic work. The suggested approach is to work on a copy of the original victim, that way the analysis process can be repeated from the beginning without losing any important data. Forensic in computer science require a perfect knowledge of hacker techniques as well as how different software works in general. Forensic science is to find evidences to make researches on it and trying to find some details and answers from it. The forensic science branch that we are interested in our thesis is computer forensics which is the same definition of forensic science but this time electronic devices are involved with our researches. The necessary data is obtained from the devices, and forensic investigators make deeper examination on them. There are several roles and responsibilities for forensic investigation. Forensic investigation is done with first responders, investigators, technicians, evidence custodians, forensic examiners and forensic analysts. (Kipper G., (2007)). The different honeypots we studied offered us several log files that a forensic party can analyze. The most common file to study when we talk about network security is the .pcap file that most honeypots are generating. This file contains all the packets exchanged between the attacker and its target. It can be opened with Wireshark and allow the forensic to see what communication happened. This file can be huge in size but contains very important information. The difficulty here is to sort the relevant information. In the case of a honeypot, we assume that all traffic is suspicious thus any IP address not within our network must be analyzed. This make the sorting easier than on a production network where the attack is harder to detect. Another part of the forensic work is called reverse engineering. When a hacker successfully compromises a system, he will most likely upload one or more malware. Reverse engineering take a closer look at these malware by decompiling it and trying to understand what are their purposes and how they work. Again this technique is very time consuming but can allow the forensics team to identify new threats. Honeypot system In the computer network is very important for network security, especially related to applications involving various interests, there will be many things that can disrupt the stability of the computer network connection, whether related to hardware (physical security, power resources) and related to software (System, configuration, access system, etc.). Disruption of the system can occur due to accidental factors performed by the manager (human error), but not least also caused by a third party. Disturbances can include destruction, infiltration, theft of access rights, misuse of data or systems, to criminal acts through computer network applications. Security of the system should be done before the system is enabled. The use of the system should be done before the actual system is enabled. Overall.

Honeypots are mostly used by military, research and government organizations. They are capturing a huge amount of information. Their aim is to discover new threats and learn more about the Blackhat motives and techniques. The objective is to learn

how to protect a system better, they do not bring any direct value to the security of an organization.

Honeyd can capture attacks and give information about the attack type and if needed, thanks to the logs, it is possible to see additional information about the attack. New attacks can be seen and new security solutions can be created by looking at them. More examinations can be obtained by looking at the type of the malicious behaviors. It helps to understand more attacks that may happen. Honeyd is not bulky in terms of capturing data. They are only dealing with the incoming malicious traffic. Therefore, the information that has been caught is not as much as the whole traffic. Focusing only on the malicious traffic makes the investigation far easier. Therefore, this makes honeyd very useful. For the only malicious traffic, there is no need for huge data storage. There is no need for new technology to maintain. Any computer can be used as a honeyd system. Thus, it does not cost additional budget to create such a system.

We studied all level of interaction honeyd and configured them. As first level of interaction honeyd, we deployed Honeyd. We explained the logic behind it and installed it correctly. Our findings about Honeyd are; Honeyd is the most popular low interaction honeyd but its problem is its age. The project is opensource but part of it is outdated and nobody seems to upgrade it. On the other hand hacker tools are evolving, so identifying this honeyd is not hard. Honeyd is using an old version on Nmap fingerprint to create fake virtual operating systems so by using a newer version of Nmap, the fake operating systems will not be recognized and Nmap will detect that there is a problem. Another limitation of Honeyd is the scripts bound to the different ports. With a basic scan it is possible to find which ports are open but as soon as the attacker tries to actually connect on a port, he will realize the service is fake. For example the script used for a Web server, by connecting it using telnet, the server should send back replies but nothing is happening. Another problem is one cannot understand if there is an incoming attack to the system or not. Because there is no such alarm system that can make you understand that there is an attack. Information gathering is not very smart either. As a result the hacker can understand quickly that there is something wrong with the target and will abort his attack. Even unprofessional intruders can compromise the honeyd without spending too much time on it. Because it is very popular and easy to use well known techniques such as Nmap. There is no additional approach needed for it. Our second step was to configure medium level interaction honeyd Nepenthes. We explained how it works and how we studied on it in implementation part. However, we found some problems with Nepenthes too. First of all, Nepenthes is for capturing malware over internet. It is mostly used for this aim. Thus, it must be implemented very rapidly since threats for users over internet are increasing dramatically day by day. Nepenthes could not keep up with new threats. As new threats are arriving and Nepenthes is not up to date, it will not be able to capture

malware. Another problem comes from the shellcode. Shellcode manager should consider about shellcode and understand it. As new threats cannot be captured, new exploits cannot be captured either. Furthermore, as we are investigating the problems and security flaws in our experiment, there is an important security flaw in Nepenthes structure. Nepenthes do not have transport layer security. Transport layer security is a protocol that gives security for communications throughout the internet. We think it is a real problem for honeypot deployment.

We explained honeypot systems in detail, and implemented low interaction, middle interaction and high interaction honeypots at laboratory. Our goal was to understand their strategy and how they are working in order to lure intruders towards the system. We discovered their security flaws in order to help researchers and organizations. Several companies are using honeypot systems to protect the whole organization's network security, and researchers are making academic experiments on them at schools. As we all know network security is very significant for all computer systems because any unprotected machine in a network can be compromised in any minute. One may lose all the secret and important data of a company, which can be a great loss, and it is also very dangerous that someone else knows your important personal information. Thus, we tried to find answers for honeypots' security using all interaction honeypots possible. Our main goal for our thesis was to see if honeypots are easy to hack and check if they are really isolated from other networks like a organization's network. When a honeypot is compromised, is it possible to reach other systems and compromise them too? After the system is compromised, is it possible to track the hacker by using necessary forensic science tools? How efficient are they? As we stated in results and analysis part, we easily hacked all the honeypots that we used for our thesis. Especially, low interaction honeypot Honeyd can be hacked easily without too much effort. As we stated before, any amateur hacker can seize the system and also can see that it is a trap system. Therefore, Honeyd is not a good honeypot as its features are not efficient to fool the hacker. As Honeyd is a daemon, it is just simulating a operating system's services. So, it is not possible to a hacker to seize other systems using Honeyd. For the intruder, it will not take time to see that the system is not real, so he will not continue compromising it. He will leave the system. For forensic part, Honeyd's log was sufficient to see the actions of the hacker. Next part was to try Nepenthes as medium interaction honeypots. The result was quite similar. Thus, we came up with this conclusion: Low interaction honeypots and medium interaction honeypots are just simulating the services of a real system, because of that it is not possible to capture significant data from intruders. They are slightly different from each other but the main idea is the same. As they are not real operating systems, it is not risky to build them. There is no need to mention about further attacks. So, we moved on to the last level. After working low interaction and medium interaction honeypots, we decided to deploy high interaction honeypots. We studied on Honeywall. Even though it is time consuming and difficult, we managed to

create a structure and worked on it. Our result were more interesting than before. High interaction honeypots are not virtualizing the system. They are real systems. So, it is very risky but the captured information is important. After deploying the implementation correctly, we successfully hacked the honeynet, but not Honeywall itself. It was the result we were looking for. As we stated in this paper, honeypot systems are still very new but are a great tool to identify cyber threats. The problem nowadays is that a very good hacker will most likely be able to understand when he is attacking a honeypot. Low interaction honeypots will be able to identify mostly automated attack and will hardly be able to understand new hacker method. On the other hand, high interaction systems are here to entrap the hacker and make him give away his techniques and tools to the forensic team. The network administrator implementing this kind of honeypot should make sure that the system is completely isolated from the production network. This is the best defense if the hacker compromises the honeypot. Network security is not a path many students are taking but we see it as one of the most important topics when we speak about computing. We were curious about this subject and decided to write a thesis on that field. This work taught us a lot about the black hat and white hat community. It also gave us an idea how huge and complex the forensic work is. New threats are discovered everyday and the best way to stay protected is to always stay up to date. By doing this simple task, most attacks will not have any effect on the system. The problem nowadays is that people using pirated version of an operating system are contributing to botnets. Their system does not support critical updates and they are more sensitive to automated attacks. Nowadays, the implementation and development of honeypots are under control by network security expert. The weakness of this system is that it is not backed up by a clear legislation. Most of the work in the future should be about improving the laws about honeypots. The current laws about honeypots in most of the countries are not clear. There is a gap between the lawyers and the IT professionals.

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